

DEEP LEARNING-BASED GEOMETRICAL ANALYSIS AND TENSION STRAIN MAPPING OF BAMBOO FIBRE MICROSTRUCTURE

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Keywords: Bamboo fibre, Microstructure, Deep-Learning Geometrical Analysis, Tension Strain Mapping, vector fields.

ABSTRACT

Bamboo technical fibre is a structurally graded natural composite material consisting of tubular elementary fibres bonded by a middle lamella. Its hierarchical design exhibits localized distortions of unknown configuration. We applied a deep learning-based geometrical analysis to extract the spatial distribution of fibre hierarchies in the cross-section, correlating this with tensile strain maps in the longitudinal direction. The lumen fraction, representing the percentage of the total technical fibre cross-sectional area occupied by lumens, averaged 7 to 13%. In the middle part of the cross-section, the middle lamella had an average thickness of 0.48 μm , while the elementary fibres averaged 13.79 μm in diameter and their lumens averaged 2.7 μm in diameter. Using vector fields derived from gradient cubic approximations, we evaluated the positional distribution of elementary fibres on the cross-section and contrasted this with micro-tensile strain maps. This analysis categorized fibre failure origins as asymmetric defibrillation and cell wall cracking, identifying key parameters for physics-informed models.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the main challenges in understanding the structural behaviour of technical bamboo fibres lies in establishing a clear relationship between their mechanical response and their complex microstructure present in the cross section. These fibres, composed of tubular elementary units bonded together by the middle lamella, form a hierarchical natural composite that features unique polygonal cell wall morphologies with internal lumens. At both the technical (fibre bundle) and elementary fibre levels, bamboo displays significant microstructural variability including distortions, surface irregularities, and cross-sectional asymmetries that have largely remained underexplored [1].

The area fraction of each anatomical phase (elementary fibre wall, lumen, and middle lamella) plays a role in defining the fiber's load-bearing capacity, as it dictates the effective cross-sectional area available for stress transfer. Such geometrical complexity results in non-uniform stiffness distributions, which may govern how damage initiates and propagates for samples without pre-existent defects. Specifically, the spatial variation in fibre cross-section is proposed as a design signature potentially linked to flexural loads experienced during the plant's growth. However, quantifying this link has been

limited by challenges in resolving these microstructures using conventional imaging. Bamboo has gained considerable attention as a natural, sustainable alternative for reinforcing composite materials due to its high strength to weight ratio, functional grading, and unique fibre architecture. Among the most studied species, *Guadua angustifolia* exhibit complex hierarchical structures, where tubular elementary fibres are bound by middle lamellae and contain central lumens. These microstructural features influence the fiber's mechanical properties, including tensile strength and stiffness, which can reach up to 800 MPa and 43 GPa, respectively [1].

Several studies have explored the mechanical behaviour of bamboo under varying loading conditions. For example, Hu et al. [2] demonstrated that strain rate sensitivity significantly affects bamboo's failure mechanisms, including fibre buckling, delamination, and intercellular cracking. Likewise, Wang et al. [3] highlighted the asymmetric bending behaviour of bamboo, driven by its gradient fiber distribution, and showed how failure initiates preferentially in parenchyma-rich zones. These investigations confirm that mechanical behaviour in bamboo is intimately tied to its internal architecture, but they often lack quantitative links between microstructure and local strain behaviour.

While scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and micro-computed tomography (μ CT) have been used to visualize damage modes and structural defects, they often fall short in segmenting distinct anatomical phases such as lumen, middle lamella, and fibre wall at the resolution needed for geometric modelling. Osorio et al. [4] conducted detailed microscopy-based studies of bamboo fibres and confirmed that variations in fiber diameter, layering patterns, and microfibrillar angles play a critical role in determining stiffness and failure. However, quantitative segmentation of these regions and their influence on strain maps remain largely unaddressed. Recent approaches have proposed nature-inspired geometrical models to replicate bamboo's toughness in synthetic structures, validating that geometry particularly gradient patterns and void distributions can drastically alter fracture behavior [5]. Yet, within the bamboo research community, there is a critical gap; the lack of computational tools to decode the spatial distribution of microstructural phases and correlate them directly with strain localization and damage asymmetry.

Despite the potential of micro-computed tomography (μ CT) to visualize complex vascular and fibrous networks in natural composites, its limited poor contrast at biological interfaces presents challenges for identifying key anatomical features, such as the middle lamella in bamboo. Recent studies have explored combining μ CT with deep learning to improve interpretability. For example, Badran et al. [6] validated the use of deep learning for segmenting low-contrast CT images of fiber-reinforced composites yet emphasized the difficulty of capturing fine features below the voxel size threshold. Similarly, deep learning-based approaches have shown promise for automating structural defect segmentation and microstructure labelling in polymer and natural composites, but their success depends heavily on high quality annotations and the amount of available domain specific training data [7, 8]. These challenges underscore the need for complementary imaging strategies. In this context, optical microscopy paired with deep learning segmentation offers a high-resolution, label-specific approach for analysing microstructural features like lumen expansion and fibre wall gradients essential for quantifying the architectural parameters that drive bamboo fibre behaviour.

However, traditional image analysis techniques such as thresholding, edge detection, and clustering are often inadequate for capturing the complex and inhomogeneous microstructures of natural fibers like bamboo [9]. To address these challenges, advanced convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been developed to enable precise semantic segmentation of hierarchical fiber structures. For instance, the CA-DeepLabv3+ model proposed by Lv et al. achieved a mean pixel accuracy of 95.2% and mean Intersection over Union (mIoU) of 90.7% across a range of natural fiber types, thanks to its attention-enhanced feature extraction and multi-scale segmentation capabilities [10]. Such architecture enables pixel-wise differentiation of critical regions such as lumens, fiber walls, and bonding interfaces. These tools offer a pathway to quantify geometrical gradients and interphase distributions, which are essential to link fiber architecture with mechanical response.

In this context, our study introduces a deep learning-based segmentation framework combined with micro-scale strain mapping to resolve the spatial hierarchy of bamboo fibre microstructures. By distinguishing lumen, middle lamella, and elementary fibre areas, and analysing their expansion gradients, we demonstrate how microstructural geometry modulates strain propagation and damage modes. This work provides novel insight into the cooperative behaviour of elementary fibres, providing quantitative geometrical links with strain and failure evolution, offering offers a foundation for bio-inspired design strategies in fibre reinforced materials.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS GENERAL SPECIFICATIONS

Single bamboo fibers were embedded in Clarocit cold-curing resin (Struers) by manually mixing 20 g of powder with 12 g of liquid hardener. The mixture was poured into silicon rubber molds initially filled halfway to position the fiber centrally before topping off to fully encapsulate it. After curing for 30 minutes and stabilizing for 24 hours at room temperature. Sectioning was performed perpendicular to the fiber's axis with the initial cutting pitch of 3 mm using a fast-trimming device for locating the fiber in the resin. Transverse finer sections were prepared using a Leica UltraCut MZ6 ultramicrotome equipped with a DIATOME Histo diamond knife (HI-14910), with cutting pitch progressively reduced from 700 nm to 250 nm. Final cuts were made at 250 nm with a holder oscillation speed of 10 mm/s to ensure flat surfaces and minimal artifact generation (see **Figure 1a** and **1b**).

Following sectioning, optical micrographs were acquired using an Olympus microscope at magnifications of 20 \times , 50 \times , and 100 \times . These scales were selected to first locate the fiber and then capture detailed regions of interest, such as lumens, middle lamella, and fiber walls. Images were recorded at a resolution of 2053 \times 1086 pixels, enabling high-fidelity input for subsequent deep learning segmentation and morphological analysis with the deep learning root painter model database trained with 1500 images.

Bamboo fibers were tested under single fiber tensile testing with a loading rate of 0.2 mm/min using FAVIMAT single fiber tensile testing equipment. The sample preparation protocol consisted of embedding the fiber to test in epoxy (28% hardener) resin blocks at each side to use them as supports avoiding damage by conventional gripping or slippage. Gage length of 15 mm was defined for the tensile tests with a total span length of 55 mm, which means that 20 mm of fiber is embedded in the resin block at each side. The protocol was designed to load the fiber from adhesive gripping from the resin with the fiber and create a homogeneous force distribution in the cross section to facilitate the damage initiation occurs in a track between the gauge length.

Figure 1. a) Fiber Sample preparation. b) Fiber Cutting by Ultramicrotomy. c) Fiber cross Section Imaging.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using Root Painter deep learning segmentation tool, we successfully resolved the three primary anatomical phases in cross-sections of bamboo technical fibres: elementary fibre walls, middle lamella, and lumens. Quantitative analysis revealed that elementary fibre walls constituted approximately 78% of the technical fibre cross-sectional area, while the middle lamella and lumens accounted for 12.9 % and 8.20%, respectively for the tested sample 1, see **Figure 2a** and **2b** (Sample1). Within an analysed area of $8214 \mu\text{m}^2$ in the fibre cross-section (1033×541 sampled pixels), 25 lumen areas were calculated and sorted from minimum to maximum to determine the rate of change of lumen size within this area, based on a linear fitting with a growth rate of 0.2 per lumen.

To sample a larger portion of the cross-section, a deeper analysis of the segmented images was performed to investigate the localised expansion and shrinkage patterns governing the area distributions and, consequently, the fibre's hierarchical organisation (see **Figure 2c**). Using the equations presented in Section 5, the scattered values (X, Y, and lumen area magnitudes) were interpolated onto a regular grid via 2D cubic interpolation, yielding a continuous vector field contour map shown in Figure 3d.

The contour-streamline map reveals a distinct pattern of peripheral intensification and central stability in pore-area ratio. Along both the left and right borders, broad bands of high gradient ($\|\nabla A\| \geq 20$) indicate pronounced expansion fronts pushing outward, likely reflecting material inhomogeneities. In contrast, the central plateau (around $X \approx 100\text{--}150 \mu\text{m}$, $Y \approx 40\text{--}80 \mu\text{m}$) remains cool and uniform ($\|\nabla A\| \leq 10$), indicating regions where pore sizes change minimally, suggesting a stable microstructure in the fibre core.

Superimposed hotspots of rapid expansion such as those near $(X, Y) \approx (230, 15)$ and $(30, 105)$ highlight localized abrupt changes area flux intensity, which may correspond to defects or transitional microdomains (see **Figure 2c** and **d**). Streamlines coherently trace these flows, converging at local maxima (possible lumens coalescence) and diverging from local minima (lumen collapse zones). Quantitatively segmenting regions above a chosen gradient threshold could enable measurement of their spatial extent providing objective metrics for comparing specimens or assessing fibre conditions.

Figure 3. (a) (b) Calculation of the Lumen expansion variation with a linear approximation applied on a lumen count on 8-bit image segmented by the deep learning approach. (c)(d) calculation of the vector field of lumen area variation

For the samples tested under tension, strain maps were calculated for two bamboo fibres. The resulting strain fields exhibited distinct oscillatory waveforms up to the point of failure, with varying percentages of strain initiation. In Sample 1, over approximately 1600 μm of fibre length, strain began to localise at around 10% of the total elongation. The characteristic damage pattern in this sample was a combination of defibrillation and partial cell wall breakage, occurring with less depth compared to Sample 2 (see **Figure 3a** and **3b**).

In contrast, Sample 2 was examined laterally, with the observation direction perpendicular to the minor width of the fibre cross section. In this case, over a 3700 μm fibre length, more pronounced oscillations were observed, with strain concentration peaking at around 40% elongation. The failure mechanism in this sample was more strongly influenced by central defibrillation, where interfacial shear stress appeared to be the dominant factor. Notably, Sample 2 also exhibited greater elongation before failure compared to Sample 1 (see **Figure 3c** and **3d**).

These patterns suggested alternating regions of higher and lower strain intensity corresponding to variations in local phase composition demonstrated in the vector fields of the cross section. Particularly, higher lumen area regions versus lower lumen area regions. Such observations support the hypothesis of mechanical cooperation among elementary fibres, where load sharing occurs along complex and asymmetric paths, likely driven by the internal geometry.

Figure 3. Strain maps applied on two bamboo fibers tested by tensile loading and strain oscillation functions. (a)(b). Sample 1. (c)(d). Sample 2

The oscillatory strain response observed along the central path of the bamboo fibre cross section is strongly indicative of an underlying structural heterogeneity presented in the cross sections studied by segmentation and gradients. Given the known anatomical features of bamboo alternating regions of vascular bundles, the higher strain amplitudes are likely associated with larger lumen fibres, while the lower amplitudes reflect more densely packed, small-lumen fibres. This interpretation is supported by the consistent periodicity and amplitude increase across different levels of applied strain, suggesting a

stable and load-sensitive mechanical differentiation and fibre cooperation. As for example, amplitude difference between the first two peaks of the strain signals was 22% in amplitude difference considering between 200 to 800 μm of fibre range at 25% of total fibre elongation in Y direction.

By analyzing the spatial strain oscillations within the 200–800 μm region, an oscillatory waveform pattern was observed in the strain signal extracted from the strain map, indicating energy dissipation along the length of the technical fiber. This behavior supports the hypothesis that internal geometry driven stiffness gradients contribute to a functionally graded mechanical response. The observed spatial damping suggests that elementary fibers cooperate mechanically, alternating in stiffness and compliance to distribute load and manage localized stress. This cooperative behavior delays failure initiation and governs the asymmetric damage evolution characteristic of bamboo technical fibers. Moreover, this difference in peak amplitude values reflect cooperative load sharing among elementary fibres. Notably, damage initiation and propagation are shown to be spatially dependent on fibre geometry and stiffness gradients. These findings support the hypothesis that microstructural geometry is a governing design parameter influencing not only failure modes (e.g., clean breakage, defibrillation, or mixed failure) but also energy dissipation and mechanical resilience.

4 EQUATIONS

To quantify the growth and shrinkage rates of the lumen size in area distributions sampling the gradient map obtained for the geometry the following equation was used:

$$\|\nabla A(x, y)\| = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial y}\right)^2}, \quad (1)$$

where $(\partial A/\partial A)$ is the partial derivative of the area in x and y direction. The expansion rate provides information regarding the geometrical features linked to dominant regions of the microstructure which can be attributed to structural changes and density variations. We point out that these regions can be extracted as indicators of stress transfer and elementary fiber cooperation. See table 1

Engineering constant	Units	Values
<i>Rate</i>	$[\mu\text{m}^2/\mu\text{m}]$	0.90
<i>Peak rate</i>	$[\mu\text{m}^2/\mu\text{m}]$	5.85
<i>Median rate</i>	$[\mu\text{m}^2/\mu\text{m}]$	0.71
<i>Percentiles</i>	$[\%]$	[0.02417066 0.06871499 0.14725231]

Table 1: rates of change of lumen area size.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study confirms that bamboo technical fibres behave as functionally graded materials, exhibiting vector fields that can be interpreted as geometrical signatures for understanding how stress is distributed and transferred axially. Fibres that demonstrated greater elongation before failure such as the second sample in the strain map showed damage initiation at approximately 20% of total elongation, compared to earlier onset in Sample 1. Microstructural geometry, including lumen expansion and phase area distribution, governs both mechanical performance and damage behaviour.

Through deep learning-based segmentation and microscale strain mapping, we identified localised regions of rapid expansion particularly around coordinates (230, 15) and (30, 105), that indicate concentrated flux activity within the lumen areas, potentially corresponding to transitional microstructural domains. The flow streamlines exhibit organised patterns, converging at areas of

maximum flux, suggestive of void coalescence, and diverging from minima, which may represent zones of maximum lumen size.

The resulting strain fields reflect cooperative mechanical behaviour, with oscillatory patterns linked to variations in material density and phase distribution. This internal structural organisation leads to asymmetric damage evolution, with clear implications for predicting failure modes. These insights suggest that geometrical characteristics can serve as predictive design parameters in composites based on bamboo, supporting quality control, process optimisation, and performance modelling.

The quantified phase proportions highlight the dominant structural role of the fibre walls in bearing load, while the middle lamella governs inter-fibre bonding and stress transfer, and the lumens influence local stress distribution and contribute to damage initiation pathways. Together, these three components define the hierarchical architecture that underpins the fibre's mechanical performance and failure behaviour. Ongoing work aims to further validate the presence of alternating regions of stiffness and compliance that enable load sharing, delay failure initiation, and govern the asymmetric damage patterns observed in bamboo technical fibres.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express their gratitude to the Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR) for supporting the SusPoCo (Sustainable Polymer Composites) project under grant agreement PRIDE21/167482260.

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